

The impact of high-temperature annealing on magnetic properties, structure and martensitic transformation of Ni₂MnGa-based glass-coated microwires

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ABSTRACT

In this article we present our experimental results on the effect of high temperature annealing on magnetic and structure performance of NiMnGa-based glass coated microwires. The samples were annealed at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1h. The as-prepared sample exhibits weak ferromagnetic behaviour with magnetic remanence near to zero and average coercivity about 6 Oe. Annealing of NiMnGa microwires leads to increase in coercivity up to 230 Oe for the sample annealed at 1273 K. Additionally, high-temperature annealing induces martensitic transformation (MT). Annealing significantly influences the Curie temperature (T_c) of the samples, bringing it closer to room temperature, thereby making them more suitable for magnetic solid-state refrigeration applications. The observed changes can be attributed to several factors, such as internal stress relaxation, nanocrystalline structure, recrystallization processes, and variations in the magnetic ordering of phases present in the as-prepared and annealed states. While the insulating and flexible glass coating enhances the mechanical properties of the microwires, it is important to acknowledge that it can also significantly affects their magnetic properties. The current results confirm the stability of ferromagnetic and martensitic transformation of nanocrystalline NiMnGa-based glass-coated wires after heat treatment up to 1273 K.

1. Introduction

Magnetic materials, particularly those Magnetic shape memory alloys (MSMAs), capable of undergoing thermoelastic martensitic phase transformations (TMPTs), have emerged as a captivating field of study due to their exceptional combination of properties [1–15]. The main advantage of these MSMAs is that they are capable to undergo large, reversible strains in response to applied magnetic fields [10–26]. In addition, these materials exhibit remarkable characteristics such as shape memory (SM), giant superelasticity (GS), magnetic field-induced strain (MFIS), and elastocaloric and magnetocaloric (MCE) effects.

This unique synergy of functionalities positions TMPT materials as promising candidates for a wide range of applications [1–28].

Among of MSMAs, Ni-Mn-Ga-based Heusler alloys are considered among the most promising magnetic shape memory alloy (MSMA) materials since the pioneering discovery of MFIS by Ullakko et al. [29]. A distinctive feature of these Ni-Mn-Ga alloys, differentiating them from the other shape memory alloys (SMAs), is their exceptionally low twinning stress, typically ranging from 0.01 to 0.5 MPa. The combination of remarkably low twinning stress and MFIS observed in Ni-Mn-Ga single crystals renders them a unique system, captivating significant research interest in both martensitic transformation and twinning

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mechanisms. Moreover, these Ni-Mn-Ga alloys have become an exciting field of study due to their unique ability to undergo a diffusionless and reversible phase transformation. This transformation involves a transition from a high-symmetry cubic austenite phase to a lower-symmetry martensite phase. This remarkable characteristic endows Ni-Mn-Ga alloys with a suite of valuable functional properties, including MSME, MFIS, and MCE [29–34]. Traditional shape memory alloys (SMAs) based on Heusler alloys exhibit a parent phase with the $L2_1$ superstructure. The martensitic transition in these alloys is accompanied by a lattice distortion, resulting in either tetragonal, orthorhombic, or monoclinic structures (Fig. 1). The specific structure depends on the chemical composition. This unique characteristic endows Heusler-based SMAs with exceptional reversibility in their shape changes between austenite and martensite phases, making them prime candidates for actuators, sensors, and energy transducers requiring high-frequency responses and substantial recoverable strains.

The ongoing trend towards miniaturization has spurred a growing demand for small-scale forms of shape memory alloy (SMA)-based devices, including particles, wires, ribbons, films, and microstructures. However, Ni-Mn-Ga alloys, which are typically classified as intermetallic compounds, exhibit inherent brittleness [30–40]. This brittleness significantly hampers their fabrication using conventional methods such as cold drawing or forging. While single crystals demonstrate enhanced ductility, their production is a time-consuming process susceptible to chemical segregation, ultimately compromising their performance [16, 18,20,21,25,26].

The Taylor-Ulitovsky method offers a promising solution for overcoming the challenges associated with fabricating Ni-Mn-Ga glass-coated microwires with different chemical composition and geometrical aspect ratios (See Fig. 2) [19,41–49]. This technique enables the production of long microwires, reaching lengths of up to 10 km with diameters between 0.1 and 100 μm [19,41–50]. Additionally, the glass coating enhances the mechanical stability of the microwire core. The cylindrical geometry of these microwires makes them well-suited for applications requiring microactuators, as they can function as thin, flexible wires. Recent research has successfully demonstrated the preparation of glass-coated microwires with a variety of chemical compositions and crystal structures, highlighting the versatility of this fabrication method [40–49].

Pioneering efforts to produce Ni-Mn-Ga glass-coated microwires date back approximately ten years [45,49]. However, early attempts encountered challenges such as manganese evaporation during fabrication, which altered the intended chemical composition, and internal stresses hindering the occurrence of the desired martensitic transformation (MT) [51–53]. Internal stresses within glass-coated microwires arise from various factors, including continuous wire drawing, rapid solidification of the metallic core, and the mismatch between the thermal expansion coefficients of the glass and metal components [50].

Recent studies have demonstrated progress in overcoming these limitations. The presence of MT has been observed in uncoated, thick Ni-Mn-Ga microwires after an annealing process [43] or after carefully performed annealing of glass-coated Ni-Mn-Ga relatively thick (above 20 μm metallic nucleus diameters) microwires at elevated temperatures [54]. Additionally, X. Zhang et al. successfully induced MT in Ni-Mn-In-Co microwires, albeit after removing the glass coating [51]. It is important to note that achieving MT has mostly been reported in microwires without a glass coating, effectively negating one of the key advantages of the Taylor-Ulitovsky technique. Nonetheless, successful attempts have been made to tailor the MT in both as-prepared and annealed NiMnGa-based glass-coated microwires [19,54]. Therefore, identifying optimal fabrication conditions remains crucial for achieving the martensitic transformation (MT) and unlocking the full potential of versatile properties within Heusler-type microwires.

This study investigates the stability of the magnetic properties and martensitic transformation (MT) behavior in thin Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs after high temperature annealing (1173 K and 1273 K for 1h). Interestingly, the extreme high post-annealing process induces a remarkable emergence of MT at low temperatures and under weak magnetic field conditions. In addition, notable improvement in the magnetic properties response due the annealing condition compared to the as-prepared sample. Where the coercivity, magnetic remanence and Curie temperature are controlled by different annealing condition.

2. Materials and method

2.1. NiMnGa-master bulk fabrication

This study focuses on the fabrication and characterization of Ni_2MnGa -based glass-coated microwires (Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs). Two main steps are needed to obtain Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs: (1) the production of a bulk Ni-Mn-Ga alloy ingot and the subsequent processing of this ingot into microwires. The initial stage involves the meticulous preparation of a $\text{Ni}_{50}\text{Mn}_{25}\text{Ga}_{25}/(\text{Ni}_2\text{MnGa})$ bulk alloy ingot through arc melting. High-purity elemental powders of nickel (Ni), manganese (Mn), and gallium (Ga), each with a purity of 99.99 wt%, are precisely weighed to achieve the desired stoichiometric composition. The weighed powders are then carefully loaded into a graphite crucible designed to withstand the high temperatures encountered during the melting process. The crucible containing the powder mixture is subsequently placed within a vacuum chamber filled with argon gas and subjected to a vacuum re-melting electric arc furnace (see Fig. 2a), inducing intense localized heat that melts the powder mixture. The melting process is meticulously controlled to ensure complete liquefaction and homogenization of the constituent elements. Following complete melting, the electric arc is extinguished, and the molten metal is allowed to cool progressively under controlled atmospheric conditions. To further refine the

Fig. 1. Illustrates the fundamental crystal structures of the austenite (a) and martensite (b) phases in Ni-Mn-Ga alloys. The colored spheres represent different crystallographic sites, with light green denoting Ga, cyan representing Ni, and pink representing Mn. Panel (c) depicts the reciprocal relationship between the two lattices. The subscripts 'a' and 'm' associated with the crystallographic axes signify austenite and martensite, respectively [36] (Reproduced from MDPI, ref. (36)). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Image of the experimental steps facility for fabrication of Ni_2MnGa glass-coated microwires. (a) Vacuum arc remelting, (b) Taylor-Ulitovski method for production of glass-coated microwires, (c) illustrate the Ni_2MnGa -based glass-coated microwires sketch.

microstructural homogeneity and elevate the overall quality of the bulk alloy, multiple remelting cycles can be implemented. This involves repeating the melting and homogenization stages, typically for 5 cycles.

2.2. NiMnGa -based glass-coated microwires preparation

Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs were fabricated using the Taylor-Ulitovsky technique with a Duran glass coating [54–58]. The microwires produced had a total diameter (D) of $26\ \mu\text{m}$ and a metallic nucleus diameter (d) of $14.1\ \mu\text{m}$ (see Fig. 2b and c). EDX analysis confirmed a chemical composition of $\text{Ni}_{54}\text{Mn}_{22}\text{Ga}_{24}$, with a deviation of approximately 0.5 % from the nominal stoichiometry. This deviation is attributed to manganese evaporation during the ingot melting and subsequent microwire preparation processes (casting and drawing). The as-prepared glass-coated microwires were encapsulated between two ceramic plates and subjected to annealing at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1 h within a vacuum environment (pressure $P = 2 \times 10^{-4}$ Pa). A heating rate of 10 K/min was employed, followed annealing and by furnace cooling. To assess the potential influence of annealing temperature, T_{ann} , on chemical composition, EDX analysis was performed following the annealing process. The analysis revealed that the chemical composition remained unchanged for the microwires annealed at 1173 K and 1273 K.

2.3. Structural and magnetic properties characterization

Structural characterization of the samples was conducted at room temperature using a Bruker D8 Discovery X-ray diffractometer equipped with $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation. The diffractometer utilized a θ - 2θ scanning geometry with a step size of 0.02° and a range of 0° – 80° .

Magnetic characterization was performed using a vibrating-sample magnetometer integrated within a Physical Property Measurement System (PPMS). Thermomagnetic characterization involved measuring magnetization as a function of temperature (T) under a constant applied magnetic field. Measurements were conducted at wide range of magnetic field 50–20000 Oe, aligned with the wire axis, within a temperature range of 5 K–400 K. A zero-field-cooled (ZFC)-field-cooled (FC)-field-heating (FH) protocol was employed to acquire the data. Initially, the sample was cooled from 400 K (paramagnetic state) in the absence of

a magnetic field. Subsequently, a chosen magnetic field was applied, and magnetization data was collected during heating to 400 K (ZFC curve). Following this, without removing the field, data were collected during cooling (FC curve) and then again during heating (FH curve). A constant heating/cooling rate of 2 K/min was maintained throughout the measurements. For hysteresis loop measurements, a vibrating-sample magnetometer was used with a maximum applied field of 30 kOe aligned along the microwire axis within the temperature range of 5 K–300 K. The Curie temperature (T_c) was determined by identifying the minimum point of the first derivative of the magnetic moment versus temperature curves. Thus, the main objective of the current study to investigate the effect of high-temperature annealing on the magneto-structural properties of NiMnGa -based glass-coated microwires.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Structure characterizations

X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected at ambient temperature for Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs. We examined the as-prepared samples and those subjected to annealing at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1 h. The XRD patterns are seen in Fig. 3. A significant wide halo is detected in the small-angle portion of the XRD pattern at roughly $2\theta = 13^\circ$ – 35° (see yellow part in Fig. 3a). This contribution, arising from the amorphous glass coating covering the NiMnGa metallic core, has been previously reported in the literature concerning glass-coated microwires [30,58, 60–63]. As-prepared Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs microwires crystallize in the austenitic (A) cubic phase at room temperature, exhibiting the Fm-3m space group and $L2_1$ ordering, which is consistent with our previous analysis of NiMnGa -based glass-coated microwires with thicker metallic nucleus diameters [60]. The ordered cubic structure of $L2_1$ is validated by the distinctive characteristics shown in the XRD profile. The as-prepared sample exhibits a distinct peak associated with the (220)A reflection at about $2\theta = 44^\circ$ and the (400)A reflection at $2\theta \approx 65.47^\circ$. In the sample annealed at 1173 K for 1 h, a new 7M orthorhombic martensite phase structure is detected with XRD peaks at $2\theta = 45.23^\circ$ and $2\theta \approx 48.1^\circ$, with reflections (022)M and (040)M. These are located next to the austenite peaks (220)A at $2\theta = 44^\circ$ and (400)A at $2\theta \approx$

Fig. 3. (a) XRD pattern measured at room temperature for as-prepared and annealed at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1h of thin NiMnGa-based glass-coated microwire. (b) Detail of the main X the Bragg Peak at $2\theta = 45^\circ$ is shown, where notable modification is observed by increasing the annealing temperature.

65.47° . In the sample subjected to high-temperature annealing at 1273 K, an additional martensitic peak emerges at $2\theta = 43.3^\circ$, corresponding to the reflection (220)M. The martensite phase peaks detected in XRD likely arise from residual martensite formed due to internal stresses during cooling, despite MT temperatures being below room temperature. Consequently, the annealing produces a martensitic phase structure in addition to the austenitic phase. The variations in diffraction intensity between the as-prepared and annealed NiMnGa-based glass-coated microwires must be attributable to alterations in the sample's microstructure caused by the annealing at selected temperature and duration.

It is possible to make an estimation of the average crystallite size (D_g) that is present within the samples using the well-known Debye-Scherrer equation (Equation (1)), provided below:

$$D_g = K\lambda / (B \cos(\theta)) \quad (1)$$

where D_g is the average crystallite size, measured in nanometers, K is the dimensionless shape factor, which is typically assumed to be 0.9, λ is the wavelength of the incident X-ray radiation (0.154 nm for Cu $K\alpha_1$ radiation), B is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of the corresponding diffraction peak, measured in radians, and θ is the Bragg angle at which the peak occurs, with 2θ being approximately 22° .

In the Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs samples, the total diffraction pattern contains the contributions from both the crystalline and amorphous phases. By analyzing the total XRD peak area in the material with mixed crystalline and amorphous structure it is possible to estimate the corresponding crystalline volume fraction, C , from the crystallinity percentage, using the following equation [64,65]:

$$C = \frac{I_c}{I_c + I_a (0.1 + e^{-D_g/25})} \quad (2)$$

where I_c represents the integrated intensity of the crystalline component, I_a represents the integrated intensity of the amorphous peak, and 25 represents a constant that is represented in nm [66]. Accordingly, we evaluated C -value for the as-prepared and annealed NiMnGa glass-coated microwires samples from the total area beneath the complete XRD peak. This content is connected to the distribution of the grains inside the crystal.

Table 1 shows that the D_g value went up significantly from 18 nm for the as-prepared sample to 62 nm for the sample that was heated to 1273 K. In the as-prepared sample C -value is about 66%. This value goes up to 88% for the sample annealed at 1173 K for 1 h and to 96% for the sample annealed at 1273 K for 1 h. In rapidly quenched materials in general and, in particular in NiMnGa alloys, heating usually produces the grains growth [54,60,64,66]. Such grain growth upon annealing is commonly associated with several processes. Thus, as the temperature rises, the atomic mobility increases, giving rise to dislocation density decrease. Additionally, the recrystallization of rapidly quenched materials occurs due to the internal stresses relaxation and the metastable structure of rapidly quenched materials. Therefore, recrystallization of amorphous phase into the stable crystalline phases takes place upon annealing. Accordingly, an increase in average grain size, D_g , upon

Table 1

Grain size average, crystalline phase content, lattice parameters and the dominant phase structure of Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs samples.

Samples	D_g (nm)	C (%)	Lattice parameter	Phase structure
As-prepared	18	66	5.767 Å	A
Anneal. at 1173 K (1h)	58	88	5.903 Å	A&M
Anneal at 1273 K (1h)	62	96	6.011 Å	A&M

annealing is commonly observed [54,59,60,64,66–69]. As we will see in the next section, a substantial change in average grain size, D_g , can greatly affect the magnetic properties of studied Ni_2MnGa glass-coated microwires.

3.2. Hysteresis loops

The hysteresis loops Ni_2MnGa -GCMWs samples, represented as the magnetization (M) as a function of the magnetic field (H), are provided in Figures (4–6). The measurements were taken at various temperatures ranging from 5 K to 300 K (room temperature). Fig. 4 presents the $M - H$ loops of Ni_2MnGa -based glass-coated microwires, both in their as-prepared and annealed states, measured at 5 K. The as-prepared sample demonstrates relatively soft magnetic properties, characterized by low magnetic remanence and coercivity. In contrast, the annealed samples exhibit increased remanence and coercivity compared to the as-prepared sample. Similar trends are observed in the $M - H$ loops measured at 100 K, as shown in Fig. 5. Notably, the hysteresis loops of the as-prepared sample remain unsaturated even at the maximum applied magnetic field of 30 kOe. Additionally, the $M - H$ loops measured at 250 K for the as-prepared sample (see Fig. 6a) reveal pronounced paramagnetic behavior. In contrast, the annealed samples exhibit ferromagnetic behavior, as observed in the hysteresis loops measured at the same temperature. The ferromagnetic contribution of both annealed samples decreases as the temperature approaches the room temperature, resulting in a mostly paramagnetic behavior characterized by a nearly linear response with negligible remanence and coercivity observed in hysteresis loops collected at $T = 300$ K. These observations indicate a magnetic phase transition from a ferromagnetic to a paramagnetic state at $T = 270$ K for annealed samples and $T = 250$ K for as-prepared samples evidenced from the hysteresis loops. The data indicate a strong relationship between the annealing conditions and the magnetic properties of the Ni_2MnGa glass-coated microwires. This relationship is further supported by the modification in the Curie

temperature (T_c). Our results reveal that the T_c of both the as-prepared and annealed samples is below room temperature. The Curie temperature of Ni_2MnGa alloys is significantly influenced by chemical composition, microstructure, manufacturing techniques, and heat treatment [52–54]. The documented range for the Curie temperature in this alloy system is from 160 K to 360 K [46,52–54,60]. Annealing can significantly influence the microstructure of Ni_2MnGa microwires, leading to tunable T_c and magnetic properties.

Fig. 7 illustrates the temperature dependencies of coercivity (H_c) and remanence (M_r) for the as-prepared and annealed samples: H_c (T) are shown in Fig. 7(a–c) and M_r (T) - in Fig. 7d. Among the samples, the one annealed at 1273 K exhibits the highest H_c -values across all measured temperatures, reaching a maximum of $H_c = 225$ Oe at 5 K and decreasing to a minimum of approximately $H_c = 5$ Oe at 270 K (see Fig. 7c). At $T = 5$ K, the H_c -value of the as-prepared sample is 15 times lower than that of the sample annealed at 1273 K and 9 times lower than the sample annealed at 1173 K. Furthermore, for the annealed samples, H_c (T) decreases monotonically as the measurement temperature increases from 5 to 300 K. As regarding M_r (T) dependence, the as-prepared sample exhibits a negligible M_r -value, with a normalized value of around 0.0001. For the sample annealed at 1173 K, M_r exhibits a complex temperature dependence, with a notable inflection point at $T = 100$ K, when the trend of $M_r(T)$ dependence changes. This inflection point corresponds to the modification in microstructure and the presence of the 7M orthorhombic martensite phase, as described in the XRD study section. For the sample annealed at 1273 K, typical ferromagnetic behavior with monotonic decrease in M_r with temperature is observed. Furthermore, the alteration in the $M_r(T)$ consisting in decreasing of M_r rate with the increase in temperature from 5 to 300 K is related to the gradual magnetic phase transition from martensite to austenite as the temperature increases. The M_r (T) and H_c (T) dependencies demonstrate the significant influence of annealing conditions on the magnetic properties of Ni_2MnGa -based glass-coated microwires.

Fig. 4. Hysteresis loops of as-prepared and annealed NiMnGa -based glass-coated microwires, treated at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1 h, measured at 5 K. (a) Full scale and (b) low scale.

Fig. 5. Hysteresis loops of as-prepared and annealed NiMnGa-based glass-coated microwires, treated at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1 h, measured at 5 K. (a) Full scale and (b) low scale.

Fig. 6. Hysteresis loops of NiMnGa-based glass-coated microwires measured at 250 K, 270 K, and 300 K, both as-prepared and after annealing at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1 h.

3.3. Magnetic and martensitic phase transitions (MT)

In Fig. 8 are presented the thermomagnetic characterization data obtained under a low magnetic field ($H = 50\text{--}200$ Oe) in the temperatures ranging from 400 K to 5 K. For the as-prepared sample, the ZFC, FC,

and FH curves exhibit significant noise due to the low magnetic signal of the as-prepared sample (vanishing remanence and low H_c value). For the samples annealed at 1173 K and 1273 K, an interesting martensite-to-austenite phase transformation is observed, where ZFC curves display a monotonic increase in magnetization with increasing temperature.

Fig. 7. Temperature dependence of In-plane coercivity (H_c) for as-prepared (a) and (b) & (c) for annealed samples at 1173 K and 1273 K for (1h), respectively. (d) Temperature dependence of In-plane remanence (M_r) for annealed samples at 1173 K and 1273 K for (1h) of NiMnGa-based glass-coated microwires (lines for eye guide).

The slope change observed at 60 K and 80 K, respectively, indicates the onset of the martensite-to-austenite phase transformation (A_{start}). The hysteresis observed between FC and FH curves (Fig. 8b and c) in both annealed samples must be attributed to the first-order martensitic phase transition (MT). Although we acknowledge that techniques such as DSC provide more precise MT onset/finish values, magnetic measurements were employed in this study due to experimental constraints and their direct relevance to the functional magnetic properties. Similar method was used in our previous study to determine MT in NiMnGa-based glass-coated microwires [54,60].

The kinks in the ZFC curves at 239 K for the sample annealed at 1173 K (see Figs. 8b) and 227 K (Fig. 8c) for the sample at annealed 1273 K correspond to the completion of austenite formation (A_{finish}). Above the structural transition temperatures ($T = 240$ K and 231 K for the samples annealed at 1173 K and 1273 K, respectively), a Hopkinson peak is observed, followed by the Curie temperature ($T_c = 272$ K and 282 K for samples annealed at 1173 K and 1273 K, respectively). The FC curve measured at ($H = 50$ Oe) for the annealed samples exhibits a small kink at 185 K (1173 K) and 210 K (1273 K), which corresponds to the Hopkinson maximum. This is followed by a further increase in magnetization up to 100 K (1173 K) and 148 K (1273 K), respectively, indicating the martensitic start temperature (M_{start}). The martensitic transformation finishes at $M_{finish} = 103$ K For (1173 K) and 148 K (1273 K), as

evidenced by the drop in magnetization.

As the applied magnetic field increases between 1 and 20 kOe, the hysteretic behavior between the FC and FH curves decreases and shifts toward the room temperature. It worth noting, the magnetic transformation is disappeared in the annealed sample by applying the external magnetic field above 10 kOe (see Fig. 9)

Figs. 8 and 9 demonstrate that the annealing significantly affects the magnetic properties and martensitic transformation (MT) behavior. The as-prepared sample demonstrates weak ferromagnetic ordering with a Curie temperature ($T_c = 220$ K) that is below the room temperature. Annealing efficiently alters the T_c towards room temperature and significantly improves the MT response. In our previous studies of thicker NiMnGa glass-coated microwires, we observed that after annealing the T_c values become close to room temperature and the as-prepared samples exhibit quite soft magnetic properties with negligible MT at low fields. The MT only was observed for the samples annealed at $T_{ann} = 973$ K and for samples annealed at lower T_{ann} the MT did not observed [46,60]. The MT observed in the studied samples annealed at $T_{ann} = 1173$ K and 1273 K for 1 h is a displacive phase change from a high-symmetry cubic austenite phase to a low-symmetry martensite phase. This change is accompanied by temperature hysteresis, usually attributed to the presence of first-order martensitic transformation [60]. Thus, the hysteresis is evident from the $M(T)$ curves

Fig. 8. ZFC-FC-FH thermomagnetic curves measured at low magnetic field (50–200 Oe) for as-prepared NiMnGa-glass-coated microwires (a) and (b)–(d) for annealed samples at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1h, respectively.

measured during heating and cooling (Fig. 8b, c, 9b, and 9c) under both low and high magnetic fields. Hence, such hysteresis clearly indicates a first-order martensitic phase transition in the microwires. This hysteresis is related to variations in the temperature dependence of the volume fraction for each phase throughout heating and cooling cycles. The transition temperatures (T_c and T_M) are predominantly determined by the chemical composition of the Ni-Mn-Ga alloy, which is typically defined by the valence electron concentration per atom (e/a) [70–72].

In addition to the disordered structure characteristic of rapidly quenched alloys, glass-coated microwires are characterized by large internal stresses (typically between 100 and 1000 MPa), originated by the rapid solidification of the metal nucleus inside a glass coating, which has significantly different thermal expansion coefficients [46,50]. Large internal stresses and the disordered crystalline structure can interfere with the martensitic transition. As discussed elsewhere [46,60], annealing allows internal stresses relaxation and structural disorder reduction. Additionally, an increase in D_g is observed (see Table 1). Accordingly, both the recrystallization process and the internal stresses relaxation enabled to substantially change T_c and achieve MT in the studied microwires.

In previous publication related to the mechanical properties of glass-coated microwires was shown, that the presence of a thin insulating and flexible glass coating, allows to enhance the poor mechanical properties of brittle nanocrystalline microwires [73]. Particularly, from the character of the sample fracture was shown that in nanocrystalline brittle microwires, the glass coating can be responsible for the sample fracture [73]. Obviously, glass-coated microwires have also better corrosion resistance and hence can protect the material from direct contact with a heat-exchange fluid. However, from the perspective of MCE applications, the role of the insulating glass coating in heat transfer was initially questionable. The answer to this question was given in our previous publications [74], where the heat exchange of a uniform glass-coated cylinder was analyzed. Provided analysis showed, that glass doesn't reduce the MCE, since it doesn't absorb the heat: all the heat released by the core is transferred to the heat-exchange fluid completely [74]. The obtained heat exchange rate allows the frequency of the magnetic refrigerators of 10 Hz, which is far beyond the current frequencies of the prototypes working usually at 0.1 Hz. Therefore, due to reduced dimensions (suitable to better heat exchange) and versatile functionalities provided by glass-coating, such microwires can potentially be suitable for MCE applications.

4. Conclusion

In summary, we observed the strong influence of the high temperature annealing on the microstructure and thermomagnetic properties of NiMnGa-based glass-coated microwire. The XRD analysis shows that the annealing enhances the formation of martensitic phase with $L2_1$ ordering, which does not exist in the as-prepared sample. In addition, the annealing promotes to increase the average grain size from 18 nm (for as-prepared sample) to 64 nm for annealed sample at 1273 K. The hysteretic behavior between FC and FH curves at a wide range of temperature and magnetic field in both annealed samples must be attributed to the enhancement of martensitic phase with $L2_1$ ordering. The experimental results are discussed within the context of the nanocrystalline structure of the as-prepared and annealed samples, encompassing the magnetic ordering of phases identified in the as-prepared state and those that emerge during the recrystallization and the internal stress relaxation after annealing. While the flexible and insulating glass coating enhances the mechanical properties of these microwires, it is essential to acknowledge its potential influence on the microstructure and magnetic properties of the NiMnGa microwires. Therefore, careful consideration of annealing conditions is crucial to achieve the desired martensitic transformation behavior. The obtained results show the suitability of NiMnGa-GCMWs annealed at high temperatures in microdevices –(sensors and actuators), energy harvesting and magnetic refrigeration.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mohamed Salaheldeen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Valentina Zhukova:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Project

Fig. 9. FC-FH thermomagnetic curves measured at high magnetic field (1–20 kOe) for as-prepared NiMnGa-glass-coated microwires (a) & (d), (b) & (e) and (c) & (f) for annealed samples at 1173 K and 1273 K for 1h, respectively.

administration, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Juan María Blanco:** Visualization, Validation, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Julian Gonzalez:** Validation, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Arcady Zhukov:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of interest

“The authors confirm that they do not have any declarations of interest.”

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References

- [1] X. Moya, S. Kar-Narayan, N.D. Mathur, Caloric materials near ferroic phase transitions, *Nat. Mater.* 13 (5) (2014) 439–450.
- [2] L. Manosa, A. Planes, Materials with giant mechanocaloric effects: cooling by strength, *Adv. Mater.* 29 (13) (2017) 1603607.
- [3] M. Salaheldeen, V. Zhukova, J. Rosero, D. Salazar, M. Ipatov, A. Zhukov, Comparison of the Magnetic and Structural Properties of MnFePSi Microwires and MnFePSi Bulk Alloy Materials, vol. 17, 2024, p. 1874, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma17081874>.
- [4] F. Guillou, G. Porcari, H. Yibole, N. van Dijk, E. Bruck, Taming the first-order transition in giant magnetocaloric materials, *Adv. Mater.* 26 (2014) 2671–2675.
- [5] D. Li, Z. Li, J. Yang, Z. Li, B. Yang, H. Yan, D. Wang, L. Hou, X. Li, Y. Zhang, et al., Large elastocaloric effect driven by stress-induced two-step structural transformation in a directionally solidified Ni₅₅Mn₁₈Ga₂₇ alloy, *Scripta Mater.* 163 (2019) 116–120.
- [6] E. Bonnot, R. Romero, L. Manosa, E. Vives, A. Planes, Elastocaloric effect associated with the martensitic transition in shape-memory alloys, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 100 (2008) 125901.
- [7] M. Salaheldeen, V. Vega, A. Ibabe, M. Jaafar, A. Asenjo, A. Fernandez, V.M. Prida, Tailoring of perpendicular magnetic anisotropy in Dy₁₃Fe₈₇ thin films with hexagonal antidot lattice nanostructure, *Nanomaterials* 8 (2018) 227.
- [8] X. Tang, Y. Feng, H. Wang, P. Wang, Enhanced elastocaloric effect and cycle stability in B and Cu co-doping Ni-Mn-In polycrystals, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 114 (2019) 033901.
- [9] M. Salaheldeen, V. Zhukova, J. Gonzalez, A. Zhukov, Anomalous magnetic behavior in MnFePSi glass-coated microwires, *J. Alloys Compd.* 1002 (2024) 175244, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2024.175244>.
- [10] B. Neese, B. Chu, S.G. Lu, Y. Wang, E. Furman, Q.M. Zhang, Large electrocaloric effect in ferroelectric polymers near room temperature, *Science* 321 (2008) 821–823.
- [11] M. Salaheldeen, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Unraveling the impact of annealing and magnetic field on MnFePSi microwires, *J. Appl. Phys.* 136 (13) (7 October 2024) 133902, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0231247>.
- [12] M. Salaheldeen, A.M. Abu-Dief, L. Martínez-Goyeneche, S.O. Alzahrani, F. Alkhatib, P. Álvarez-Alonso, J.A. Blanco, Dependence of the magnetization process on the thickness of Fe₇₀Pd₃₀ nanostructured thin film, *Materials* 13 (2020) 5788, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma13245788>.
- [13] S. Ma, X. Zhang, G. Zheng, M. Qian, L. Geng, Toughening of Ni-Mn-based polycrystalline ferromagnetic shape memory alloys, *Materials* 16 (2023) 5725.
- [14] D.Y. Cong, L. Huang, V. Hardy, D. Bourgault, X.M. Sun, Z.H. Nie, M.G. Wang, Y. Ren, P. Entel, Y.D. Wang, Low-field-actuated giant magnetocaloric effect and excellent mechanical properties in a NiMn-based multiferroic alloy, *Acta Mater.* 146 (2018) 142–151.
- [15] M. Salaheldeen, A. Talaat, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Preparation and magneto-structural investigation of nanocrystalline CoMn-based heusler alloy glass-coated microwires, *Processes* 10 (2022) 2248.
- [16] A. Wojcik, R. Chulist, P. Czaja, M. Kowalczyk, P. Zackiewicz, N. Schell, W. Maziarz, Evolution of microstructure and crystallographic texture of Ni-Mn-Ga melt-spun ribbons exhibiting 1.15% magnetic field-induced strain, *Acta Mater.* 219 (2021) 117237.
- [17] Y.F. Wu, H.C. Xuan, S. Agarwal, Y.K. Xu, T. Zhang, L. Feng, H. Li, P.D. Han, C. L. Zhang, D.H. Wang, et al., Large magnetocaloric effect and magnetoresistance in Fe and Co co-doped Ni-Mn-Al Heusler alloys, *Phys. Status Solidi* 215 (2018) 1700843.
- [18] V. Franco, J.S. Blázquez, J.J. Ipus, J.Y. Law, L.M. Moreno-Ramírez, A. Conde, Magnetocaloric effect: from materials research to refrigeration devices, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 93 (2018) 112–232.

- [19] M. Salaheldeen, V. Zhukova, R. Lopez Anton, A. Zhukov, Dependence of magnetic properties of as-prepared nanocrystalline Ni₂MnGa glass-coated microwires on the geometrical aspect ratio, *Sensors* 24 (2024) 3692, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24113692>.
- [20] T. Graf, S.S.P. Parkin, C. Felser, Heusler compounds—a material class with exceptional properties, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* 47 (2011) 367–373.
- [21] K. Otsuka, C.M. Wayman, *Shape Memory Materials*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK, 1999.
- [22] M. Salaheldeen, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Unraveling the impact of annealing and magnetic field on MnFePSi microwires, *J. Appl. Phys.* 136 (13) (2024) 133902, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0231247>, 7 October.
- [23] R. Cesare, J. Pons, R. Santamarta, C. Seguí, V.A. Chernenko, Ferromagnetic shape memory alloys: an overview, *Arch. Metall. Mater.* 49 (2004) 779–789.
- [24] M. Salaheldeen, V. Vega, R. Caballero-Flores, V.M. Prida, A. Fernández, Influence of nanoholes array geometrical parameters on magnetic properties of Dy-Fe antit dot thin films, *Nanotechnology* 30 (2019) 455703.
- [25] K. Otsuka, X. Ren, Physical metallurgy of Ti-Ni-based shape memory alloys, *Prog. Mater. Sci.* 50 (2005) 511–678.
- [26] J. Wilson, M. Weselowski, Shape memory alloys for seismic response modification: a state-of-the-art review, *Earthq. Spectra* 21 (2005) 569–601.
- [27] J. Dong, C. Cai, A. Okeil, Overview of potential and existing applications of shape memory alloys in bridges, *J. Bridge Eng.* 16 (2011) 305–315.
- [28] V.A. Lobodyuk, Y.N. Koval, V.G. Pushin, Crystal-structural features of pretransition phenomena and thermoelastic martensitic transformations in alloys of nonferrous metals, *Phys. Met. Metallogr.* 111 (2011) 165–189.
- [29] K. Ullakko, J.K. Huang, C. Kantner, R.C. O’Handley, V.V. Kokorin, Large magnetic field-induced strains in Ni₂MnGa single crystals, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 69 (1996) 1966, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.117637>.
- [30] M. Salaheldeen, A. Wederni, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Preparation and magneto-structural investigation of high-ordered (L₂ structure) Co₂MnGe microwires, *Processes* 11 (2023) 1138.
- [31] D.Y. Cong, W.X. Xiong, A. Planes, Y. Ren, L. Mañosa, P.Y. Cao, Z.H. Nie, X.M. Sun, Z. Yang, X.F. Hong, et al., Colossal elastocaloric effect in ferroelastic Ni-Mn-Ti alloys, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 122 (2019) 255703.
- [32] J.D. Callaway, R.F. Hamilton, H. Schitoglu, N. Miller, H.J. Maier, Y. Chumlyakov, Shape memory and martensite deformation response of Ni₂MnGa, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 16 (2007) S108–S114.
- [33] J. Pons, E. Cesari, C. Seguí, F. Masdeu, R. Santamarta, Ferromagnetic shape memory alloys: alternatives to Ni–Mn–Ga, *Mater. Sci. Eng.* 481–482 (2008) 57–65.
- [34] V.G. de Paula, M.S. Reis, All-d-metal full heusler alloys: a novel class of functional materials, *Chem. Mater.* 33 (2021) 5483–5495.
- [35] Z.Y. Wei, E.K. Liu, J.H. Chen, Y. Li, G.D. Liu, H.Z. Luo, X.K. Xi, H.W. Zhang, W. H. Wang, G.H. Wu, Realization of multifunctional shape-memory ferromagnets in all-d-metal Heusler phases, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 107 (2015).
- [36] L. Righi, Neutron diffraction study of the martensitic transformation of Ni_{2.07}Mn_{0.93}Ga heusler alloy, *Metals* 11 (2021) 1749, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met1111749>.
- [37] Y. Zhang, R.A. Hughes, J.F. Britten, P.A. Dube, J.S. Preston, G.A. Botton, M. Niewczas, Magnetocaloric effect in Ni–Mn–Ga thin films under concurrent magnetostructural and curie transitions, *J. Appl. Phys.* 110 (2011) 013910.
- [38] Z.B. Li, J.L. Sánchez Llamazares, C.F. Sánchez-Valdés, Y.D. Zhang, C. Esling, X. Zhao, L. Zuo, Microstructure and magnetocaloric effect of melt-spun Ni₅₂Mn₂₆Ga₂₂ ribbon, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 100 (2012) 174102.
- [39] J. Wang, C. Jiang, R. Techapiesanchaorenkij, D. Bono, S.M. Allen, R.C. O’Handley, Microstructure and magnetic properties of melt spinning Ni–Mn–Ga, *Intermetallics* 32 (2013) 151–155.
- [40] F.H. Chen, M.G. Zhang, Y.S. Chai, C.W. Gong, Martensitic structure and magnetic domain transformation in melt-spun Ni–Mn–Ga ferromagnetic ribbons, *Phys. Status Solidi A* 209 (2012) 1557–1561.
- [41] M.F. Qian, X.X. Zhang, L.S. Wei, P. Martín, J.F. Sun, L. Geng, T.B. Scott, H.Z. Peng, Tunable magnetocaloric effect in Ni–Mn–Ga microwires, *Sci. Rep.* 8 (2018) 16574.
- [42] M.F. Qian, X.X. Zhang, X. Li, R.C. Zhang, P.G. Martin, J.F. Sun, L. Geng, T.B. Scott, H.Z. Peng, Magnetocaloric effect in bamboo-grained Ni–Mn–Ga microwires over a wide working temperature interval, *Mater. Des.* 190 (2020) 108557.
- [43] P. Zheng, N.J. Kucza, C.L. Patrick, P. Müllner, D.C. Dunand, Mechanical and magnetic behavior of oligocrystalline Ni–Mn–Ga microwires, *J. Alloys Compd.* 624 (2015) 226–233, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2014.11.067>.
- [44] M. Salaheldeen, A. Wederni, M. Ipatov, J. Gonzalez, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Elucidation of the strong effect of the annealing and the magnetic field on the magnetic properties of Ni₂-based heusler microwires, *Crystals* 12 (2022) 1755, <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst12121755>.
- [45] Z. Ding, J. Zhu, X. Zhang, D. Liu, Q. Qi, Y. Zhang, D. Cong 14% recoverable strain in Ni_{52.87}Mn_{23.82}Ga_{23.32} microwires, *J. Appl. Phys. D.* (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/aa5609>.
- [46] A. Zhukov, P. Corte-Leon, L. Gonzalez-Legarreta, M. Ipatov, J.M. Blanco, A. Gonzalez, V. Zhukova, Advanced functional magnetic microwires for technological applications, *J. Phys. D Appl. Phys.* 55 (2022) 253003, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ac4fd7>.
- [47] R. López Antón, J.P. Andrés, J.A. González, A. García-Gómez, V. Zhukova, A. Chizhik, M. Salaheldeen, A. Zhukov, Tuning of magnetic properties and Giant Magnetoimpedance effect in multilayered microwires, *J. Sci.: Advanced Materials and Devices* (2024) 100821, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsamd.2024.100821>.
- [48] Y. Zhang, M. Li, Y.D. Wang, J.P. Lin, K.A. Dahmen, Z.L. Wang, P.K. Liaw, Superelasticity and serration behavior in small-sized NiMnGa alloys, *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 16 (2014) 955–960, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.201300518>.
- [49] A. Zhukov, C. Garcia, M. Ilyn, R. Varga, J.J. DelVal, A. Granovsky, V. Rodionova, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, Magnetic and transport properties of granular and Heusler-type glass-coated microwires, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 324 (2012) 3558–3562, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2012.02.089>.
- [50] H. Chiriac, T.A. Ovári, G. Pop, Internal stress distribution in glass-covered amorphous magnetic wires, *Phys. Rev. B* 52 (1995) 10104–10113, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.52.10104>.
- [51] X.X. Zhang, S.P. Miao, J.F. Sun, Magnetocaloric effect in Ni–Mn–In–Co microwires prepared by Taylor-Ulitovsky method, *Trans. Nonferrous Metals Soc. China* 24 (2014) 3152–3157, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326\(14\)63454-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326(14)63454-3) (English Ed).
- [52] A. Zhukov, M. Ipatov, J.J. del Val, V.A. Chernenko, V. Zhukova, Tailoring of magnetic properties of Heusler-type glass-coated microwires by annealing, *J. Alloys Compd.* 732 (2018) 561–566.
- [53] A. Zhukov, Ipatov, J.J. del Val, P. Corte-León, J. Gonzalez, A. Granovsky, V. Zhukova, Effect of annealing on magnetic properties of Ni–Mn–Ga glass-coated microwires, *J. Mater. Res.* 33 (2018) 2148–2155.
- [54] A. Zhukov, M. Ipatov, J.J. Del Val, S. Taskaev, M. Churyukanova, V. Zhukova, First-order martensitic transformation in heusler-type glass-coated microwires, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 111 (2017) 242403.
- [55] A. Zhukov, V. Zhukova, J.M. Blanco, J. Gonzalez Recent research on magnetic properties of glass-coated microwires, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 294 (2005) 182–192, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmmm.2005.03.033>.
- [56] M. Salaheldeen, V. Zhukova, M. Ipatov, A. Zhukov, Unveiling the magnetic and structural properties of (X₂YZ; X = Co and Ni, Y = Fe and Mn, and Z = Si) full-heusler alloy microwires with fixed geometrical parameters, *Crystals* 13 (2023) 1550, <https://doi.org/10.3390/cryst13111550>.
- [57] A. Wederni, M. Salaheldeen, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Influence of the geometrical aspect ratio on the magneto-structural properties of Co₂MnSi microwires, *Metals* 13 (2023) 1692, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13101692>.
- [58] M. Salaheldeen, A. Wederni, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Carbon-Doped Co₂MnSi heusler alloy microwires with improved thermal characteristics of magnetization for multifunctional applications, *Materials* 16 (2023) 5333.
- [59] V.A. Chernenko, M. Ohtsuka, M. Kohl, V.V. Khovailo, T. Takagi, Transformation behavior of Ni–Mn–Ga thin films, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 14 (2005) S245–S252.
- [60] A. Zhukov, M. Ipatov, J.J. del Val, et al., Magnetic and structural properties of glass-coated Heusler-type microwires exhibiting martensitic transformation, *Sci. Rep.* 8 (2018) 621, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-19032-z>.
- [61] M. Salaheldeen, A. Garcia-Gomez, M. Ipatov, P. Corte-Leon, V. Zhukova, J. M. Blanco, A. Zhukov, Fabrication and magneto-structural properties of Co₂-based heusler alloy glass-coated microwires with high curie temperature, *Chemosensors* 10 (2022) 225, <https://doi.org/10.3390/chemosensors10060225>.
- [62] M. Salaheldeen, M. Ipatov, P. Corte-Leon, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Effect of annealing on the magnetic properties of Co₂MnSi-based heusler alloy glass-coated microwires, *Metals* 13 (2023) 412, <https://doi.org/10.3390/met13020412>.
- [63] M. Salaheldeen, A. Wederni, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, R. Lopez Anton, A. Zhukov, Enhancing the squareness and Bi-phase magnetic switching of Co₂FeSi microwires for sensing application, *Sensors* 23 (2023) 5109, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s23115109>.
- [64] M.F. Cerqueira, M. Stepikhova, A. Kozanecki, G. Andrés, E. Alves, Crystal size and crystalline volume fraction effects on the erbium emission of nc-Si:Er grown by r.f. sputtering, *J. Nanosci. Nanotechnol.* 10 (2010) 2663–2668, <https://doi.org/10.1166/jnn.2010.1380>.
- [65] M. Salaheldeen, A. Garcia, P. Corte-Leon, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, A. Zhukov, Unveiling the effect of annealing on magnetic properties of nanocrystalline half-metallic heusler Co₂FeSi alloy glass-coated microwires, *J. Mater. Res. Technol.* 20 (2022) 4161–4172.
- [66] M.F. Cerqueira, M. Andritschky, L. Rebouta, J.A. Ferreira, M.F. da Silva, Macrocrystalline silicon thin films prepared by RF reactive magnetron sputter deposition, *Vacuum* 46 (1995) 1385–1390, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0042-207X\(95\)00158-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0042-207X(95)00158-1).
- [67] V. Zhukova, A.F. Cobeño, A. Zhukov, J.M. Blanco, V. Larin, J. Gonzalez, Coercivity of glass-coated Fe_{73.4-x}Cu₁Nb_{3.1}Si_{13.4+x}B_{9.1} (0 ≤ x ≤ 1.6) microwires, *Nanostruct. Mater.* 11 (1999) 1319–1327, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0965-9773\(99\)00424-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0965-9773(99)00424-9).
- [68] A.L. Greer, Crystallization of amorphous alloys, *Metall. Mater. Trans.* 27 (1996) 549–555, <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02648945>.
- [69] G. Herzer, Grain size dependence of coercivity and permeability in nanocrystalline ferromagnets, *IEEE Trans. Magn.* 26 (1990) 1397–1402, <https://doi.org/10.1109/20.104389>.
- [70] V.A. Chernenko, V.A. L’vov, S.P. Zagorodnyuk, T. Takagi, Ferromagnetism of thermoelastic martensites: theory and experiment, *Phys. Rev. B* 67 (2003) 064407.
- [71] S.K. Wu, S.T. Yang, Effect of composition on transformation temperatures of Ni–Mn–Ga shape memory alloys, *Mater. Lett.* 57 (2003) 4291–4296.
- [72] V.A. Chernenko, Compositional instability of β-phase in Ni–Mn–Ga alloys, *Scripta Mater.* 40 (1999) 523–527.
- [73] V. Zhukova, A.F. Cobeño, A. Zhukov, A.R. de Arellano Lopez, S. López-Pombero, J. M. Blanco, V. Larin, J. Gonzalez, Correlation between magnetic and mechanical properties of devitrified glass-coated Fe_{71.8}Cu₁Nb_{3.1}Si₁₅B_{9.1} microwires, *J. Magn. Magn. Mater.* 249 (P1-II) (2002) 79–84.
- [74] A. Zhukov, V. Rodionova, M. Ilyn, A.M. Aliev, R. Varga, S. Michalik, A. Aronin, G. Abrosimova, A. Kiselev, M. Ipatov, V. Zhukova, Magnetic properties and magnetocaloric effect in Heusler-type glass-coated NiMnGa microwires, *J. Alloys Compd.* 575 (2013) 73–79, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2013.04.083>.